

NONLINEAR VISCOELASTIC CHARACTERIZATION OF IM7/RP46 LAMINATES AT HIGH TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Short-term creep and recovery tests are performed on IM7/RP46 composites at several fixed high temperatures and stress levels with the aim of predicting the long-term laminate mechanical properties. The glass transition temperature is determined for the RP46 resin, and IM7/RP46 composite material is examined using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) in order to determine an acceptable range of creep/recovery test temperatures. A predictive nonlinear viscoelastic model is used to predict the long-term behavior of the composites in terms of master curves extrapolated from the short term tests.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are increasingly being expected to serve in extreme environments which previously only metals could withstand. The next generation of transport aircraft designed for flying at supersonic speeds and Single-Stage-To-Orbit (SSTO) vehicles are not feasible without the usage of polymeric composites to reduce the weight of the vehicle's structure. Therefore, there is a great desire for polymeric composites that can survive in severe environments and yet retain good properties. Unfortunately, the typical polymeric matrices in common use today (epoxies, etc.) simply can not withstand the temperatures likely to be encountered by composite structures in these advanced designs.

The polyimide matrix resin known as LaRC-RP46 was developed in an attempt to provide structurally efficient advanced composites for service in high-temperature applications. Various experimental studies have shown that these composites possess higher fracture toughness and strength than the current industry standard PMR-15 polyimide matrix resin [1-4]. Recent studies have also shown that composites based on RP46 retain higher mechanical properties at temperatures up to 700°F and provide greater resistance to microcracking than PMR-15 based composites [1-4]. However, there is little information concerning the long term mechanical

behavior and life prediction of RP46 composites. In addition, it is not economically feasible to test the composite structures in question under service conditions for a typical design lifetime. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an accelerated test methodology for the composite laminates. This is accomplished for laminates of IM7/RP46 by using Schapery's nonlinear viscoelastic model to predict the long-term behavior of the composites in terms of master curves developed from short-term creep/recovery tests.

THEORETICAL

Schapery's nonlinear viscoelastic model [5] is described as:

$$\epsilon(t) = g_o A_o \sigma_o + g_1 \int_0^t \Delta A(\Psi - \Psi') \frac{\partial(g_2 \sigma_o)}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \alpha \Delta T \tag{1}$$

with Ψ the reduced time defined as

$$\Psi = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma a_\tau} \quad \Psi' = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma a_\tau} \tag{2}$$

where A_o and ΔA are the initial and transient components of the transverse creep compliance. α is the thermal expansion coefficient of the composite in the transverse direction; ΔT is the temperature difference from the stress-free state. It can be assumed the transient component of the creep compliance, $\Delta A(\Psi)$ can be approximated as a power law form:

$$\Delta A(\Psi) = C \Psi^n \tag{3}$$

with C and n material constants independent of stress level [6]. In order to obtain the unknown functions in Eqn. (1), creep and subsequent recovery tests need to be performed. It can be shown from Eqn. (1) and assumption of the power law approximation in Eqn. (3) that the creep strain ϵ_c is represented by:

$$\epsilon_c(t) = \left[g_o A_o + \frac{C g_1 g_2}{a_\sigma^n a_\tau^n} t^n \right] \sigma + \alpha \Delta T \quad 0 < t < t_1 \tag{4}$$

and that the recovery strain ϵ_r can be written as:

$$\epsilon_r(t) = \frac{\Delta \epsilon}{g_1} \left[(1 + a_\sigma a_\tau \lambda)^n - (a_\sigma a_\tau \lambda)^n \right] + \alpha \Delta T \quad t > t_1 \tag{5}$$

$$\Delta \epsilon = \frac{C g_1 g_2 t_1^n}{a_\sigma^n a_\tau^n} \sigma \tag{6}$$

The nondimensional time scale λ in Eqn. (5) is given by

$$\lambda = \frac{t - t_1}{t_1} \tag{7}$$

where t_1 is the time at the termination of the creep test [5-8].

Originally, the viscoelastic parameters were determined by graphically shifting techniques [5-6], but those techniques were tedious and could be somewhat subjective in nature. It was also

difficult to incorporate such techniques into computer programs. Using a numerical technique alone or in combination with graphical techniques reduces the time required for the analysis of the experimental data and eases the incorporation of the resulting model into a computer routine. The numerical approach was advanced by several researchers [7-8]. Equations (4) and (5) are of considerable use with regards to this technique.

Equations (4) and (5) can be used for the determination of the viscoelastic parameters in Equation (1) by using a nonlinear regression curve-fitting technique. Using Equation (4) for the first portion of the test (i.e. the creep phase) and using Equation (5) for the second portion of the test (i.e. the recovery phase) it is possible to resolve the various parameters [5-8].

EXPERIMENTAL

The LaRC-RP46 resin system is a PMR type polyimide produced from the following three monomer reactants:

- monomethyl ester of 5-norbornene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (NE)
- 3,4'-oxydianiline (3,4'-ODA)
- dimethyl ester of 3,3',4,4'-benzophenonetetracarboxylic acid (BTDE)

according to the stoichiometric ratios of NE : 3,4'-ODA : BTDE = 2.0 : 3.087 : 2.087 [1]. This combination produced a theoretical formulated molecular weight (M_w) between crosslink sites of 1,500 g/mole [2]. This formulated molecular weight was chosen due to its high glass transition temperature (T_g) and relative ease of processing. In order to determine the T_g of the RP46 resin, DSC and rheological data were examined. Figure 1 illustrates rheological data used to determine the glass transition temperature. It can be seen that the location of the G'' peak occurs at approximately 310°C.

Figure 1: Rheological Data for LaRC-RP46

Using prepreg produced at the NASA Langley Research Center, a series of 15 x 15 cm RP46 panels were manufactured using a optimized "dry" molding cycle of the following three layups: $[0]_{10}$, $[90]_{10}$, and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ [3]. The panels were C-scanned to verify that the panels were of the highest possible quality. The fiber volume fractions of the panels was determined using optical microscopy and found to be equal to 63.8%. The optical microscopy also indicated a near-zero percentage of voids.

The general purpose finite element package ANSYS was used to model a series of possible test specimen geometries in order to assure a uniform state of strain in the central region of the specimens. Based on the results of this finite element study and the test fixture configuration, it was found that for the longitudinal and transverse specimens; a length of 15 cm and a width of 1.27 cm was satisfactory. However, for the shear specimens, a length of 15 cm and a width of 2.54 cm was necessary to insure a uniform shear stress in the region of the strain gages.

The Instron hydraulic test machine was programmed to subject the specimens to stresses ranging from 10 MPa to 20 MPa for 60 minutes followed by a 60 minute recovery phase. These stress histories were repeated at 177°C, 204°C, 288°C, 316°C, and 325°C for the transverse specimens and 177°C, 204°C, 260°C, and 288°C for the shear specimens. Note that it was necessary to double the load applied to the shear specimens. This is due to the fact that the shear stress in the $\pm 45^\circ$ shear specimens was equal to one-half the applied tensile load. Therefore, applying a tensile stress of σ_x yielded a shear stress of $1/2 \sigma_x$ [10-11].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formation of the IM7/RP46 master curves necessitated the determination of the eight viscoelastic parameters A_0 , C , n , g_0 , g_1 , g_2 , a_σ , and a_T . Since A_0 , C , and n were assumed to be independent of temperature or stress level [6-8], they were calculated at the lowest temperature and stress level and assumed to be constant. The parameter a_σ was determined at each temperature by setting it equal to one at the reference stress level of 10.3 MPa and calculating its value at all other stress levels referenced to that stress level. Similarly, the parameter a_T was determined by setting it equal to one at the reference temperature of 177°C and calculating its value at all other temperatures referenced to that temperature. The remaining parameters g_0 , g_1 , and g_2 were then calculated by fitting the experimental creep and recovery data to Equations 4 and 5 by means of the nonlinear regression curve-fitting routines in the software packages Mathematica V2.2.1 and Deltagraph Pro. The values obtained for A_0 , C , and n are listed in Table 1. Note that as the S_{11} and S_{12} compliance terms were insensitive to time, it was only necessary to examine the S_{22} and S_{66} terms in detail [9, 11].

Table 1: A_0 , C , and n for Transverse and Shear Terms

Compliance Term	A_0 (%/cm ²)	C (%/cm ² -sec)	n
S_{22}	1.4513×10^{-5}	3.2116×10^{-7}	0.161
S_{66}	2.0795×10^{-4}	4.7210×10^{-7}	0.248

The parameters g_0 , g_1 , and g_2 for the S_{22} compliance term were all found to be approximately equal to one. Thus, only horizontal shifts due to stress and temperature were necessary to form the S_{22} master curve. However, they were not equal to one for the S_{66} case except at the reference stress level. Figure 2 contains the values obtained for a_σ for the S_{22} case, and figures 3-4 contain the values obtained for g_0 , g_1 , g_2 , and a_σ for the S_{66} case.

Figure 2: Parameter a_T^n for S_{22} and S_{66} and Parameter a_σ for S_{22} Term

Figure 3: Parameters g_0 and g_1 for the S_{66} Term

Figure 4: Parameters g_2 and a_σ for the S_{66} Term

Since S_{11} and S_{12} were assumed to be time, temperature, and stress independent, it was only necessary to form master curves for the S_{22} and S_{66} terms [9, 11]. Using the Time-Temperature-Stress-Superposition Principle (TTSSP) mentioned previously [8], master curves were formed for the S_{22} and S_{66} compliance terms of a lamina of IM7/RP46. Figure 5 contains the master curves obtained for the S_{22} and S_{66} cases.

Figure 5: S_{22} and S_{66} Master Curves

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated experimentally that Schapery's nonlinear constitutive viscoelastic model can be successfully used to characterize the long term behavior of laminates of IM7/RP46. By using a nonlinear viscoelastic theory, it is possible to predict the behavior of the laminates at higher levels of stress and strain than would be possible with a linear viscoelastic model. This is especially important due to the type of applications which might employ RP46 composites. This model has also been shown to be relatively simple to incorporate into computer programs based on Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) [7]. Thus, by using this model to characterize the behavior of a lamina of IM7/RP46, it can be used to predict the long term behavior of a general laminate of IM7/RP46.

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